

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate

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Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of formic and oxalic acids by benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate (BTMACB) have been studied in acetic acid-water (1 : 1) solutions. The main product of oxidation is carbon dioxide. The reaction is first order with respect to BTMACB. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics were observed with respect to the reductants. The oxidation of α -deuterioformic acid (DFA) exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect ($k_H/k_D = 5.30$ at 298 K). The reaction has been studied in solvents of different compositions of acetic acid and water. The solvent composition effect has been analysed using Grunwald-Weinstein equation. Suitable mechanisms have been proposed.

Benzyltrimethylammonium chlorobromate (BTMACB) is one of the quarternary ammonium polyhalides which has been used as an effective halogenating and oxidizing agent in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻³. Polymeric benzyltrimethylammonium dichloroiodate and dibromoiodate have been used for the addition of halogens to olefins⁴. The polyhalides are more suitable than molecular halogens because of their solid nature, ease of handling, stability, selectivity and excellent product yield. We have been interested in the kinetic and mechanistic aspects of oxidation by polyhalogen compounds and many reports have emanated from our laboratory⁵⁻⁸. Only a few reports regarding the mechanistic aspects of the oxidations by BTMACB have been reported⁹⁻¹². There seems to be no report on the kinetics oxidation of organic acids by BTMACB. In continuation of our earlier studies, we report here in the kinetics of oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by BTMACB in aqueous acetic acid as solvent. Suitable mechanisms have also been proposed.

Results and discussion

The oxidation of organic acids leads to the formation of carbon dioxide. The stoichiometric determination indicated the following overall reactions :

Rate laws : The reactions were found to be first order with respect to BTMACB. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , is independent of the initial concentra-

tion of BTMACB. The reaction rate increases with an increase in [organic acid] but not linearly (Table 1). A plot of $1/[\text{organic acid}]$ versus $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ is linear with an intercept on the rate ordinate. Thus the reactions exhibited Michaelis-Menten type kinetics with respect to the organic acids. This indicates the following overall mechanism (3) and (4) and the rate law (5).

$$\text{Rate} = k_2 K [\text{oxidant}][\text{organic acid}] / (1 + K [\text{organic acid}]) \quad (5)$$

The dependence of the reaction rate on reductant concentration was studied at different temperatures and the values of K and k_2 were evaluated from the double reciprocal plots. The thermodynamic and activation parameters, at 298 K, were also calculated from the values of K and k_2 respectively, at four different temperatures (Tables 2 and 3).

Induced polymerization of acrylonitrile : The oxidation of organic acids by BTMACB, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate (Table 1).

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, the oxidation of DFA was studied. The results recorded in Tables 2 and 3, showed that while the formation constant, K , for the ordinary and deuteriated formic acids have almost identical values, the rate constant for the decomposition of the complex, k_2 , exhibited a substantial primary kinetic

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of oxalic and formic acids by BTMACB at 298 K

10 ³ [BTMACB] [Organic acid]		10 ⁴ k _{obs} s ⁻¹	
mol dm ⁻³	mol dm ⁻³	Oxalic acid	Formic acid
1.00	0.10	27.8	4.11
1.00	0.20	34.6	6.22
1.00	0.40	39.5	8.37
1.00	0.60	41.5	9.46
1.00	0.80	42.6	10.1
1.00	1.00	43.3	10.6
1.00	1.50	44.2	11.2
1.00	3.00	45.1	12.0
2.00	0.20	34.1	6.00
4.00	0.20	35.6	6.76
6.00	0.20	35.0	6.26
8.00	0.20	34.8	6.10
1.00	0.20	34.2*	6.55*

*Contained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Effect of solvent composition : The rate constant of oxidation was determined in solvents containing different amounts of acetic acid and water. It was observed that the rate constant increased with an increase in the amount of water in the solvent mixture. To determine whether the solvent composition is affecting the formation constant, *K*, and/or rate constant, *k*₂, the variation of rate with the concentration of formic acid was studied in solutions of different compositions. The results (Table 5) showed the rate constants, *k*₂, vary considerably while the formation constant, *K*, remained practically independent of solvent composition.

We have carried out some conductivity measurements to determine the nature of BTMACB in aqueous acetic acid solution⁹. It was observed that acetic acid has very low conductivity. Addition of BTMACB increases the conductivity of acetic acid. We measured the conductivity of BTMACB in solvents containing different proportions of acetic acid (100–30%) and water also. We found that the

Table 2. Formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of the organic acids-BTMACB complexes

Subst.	K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)				Δ <i>H</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> [‡] (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Δ <i>G</i> [‡] (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
OA	31.4	15.1	7.00	3.57	-58.0 ± 0.6	-164 ± 2	-9.15 ± 0.5
FA	5.92	4.72	3.76	3.02	-21.1 ± 0.8	-51 ± 3	-6.31 ± 0.6
DFA	6.45	5.21	4.34	3.41	-18.4 ± 0.5	-40 ± 2	-6.58 ± 0.4

Table 3. Rate constants and activation parameters of the oxidation of organic acids by BTMACB

Subst.	10 ⁴ k ₂ /(dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				Δ <i>H</i> [*] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	Δ <i>S</i> [*] (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Δ <i>G</i> [*] (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
OA	22.4	46.1	92.2	188	51.3 ± 0.7	-118 ± 2	86.3 ± 0.6
FA	6.15	12.8	25.1	52.5	51.5 ± 0.9	-128 ± 3	89.5 ± 0.7
DFA	1.03	2.25	4.58	9.81	54.3 ± 0.7	-133 ± 2	93.8 ± 0.6
k _H /k _D	5.97	5.69	5.48	5.35			

Table 4. Effect of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride/bromide ion on the rate of oxidation of oxalic acid by BTMACB

[BTMACB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [oxalic acid] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 298 K

10 ⁵ k _{obs} /s ⁻¹	0.00	0.20	0.40	0.60	0.80	1.00
BTMACl	43.3	44.1	43.0	44.6	42.1	44.0
Br	43.3	42.2	44.3	42.5	42.8	44.4

isotope effect (Table 3).

Effect of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride or bromide ions : Rates of oxidation were not affected by the addition of benzyltrimethylammonium chloride (BTMACl) or potassium bromide (KBr) (Table 4).

conductivity increases sharply as the water content is initially increased but reaches a limiting value in about 60% acetic acid-water mixture. Therefore, BTMACB can be considered as an ionic compound, which exists under the reaction conditions as benzyltrimethylammonium and chlorobromate ions [eq. (6)]. No effect of added benzyltrimethylammonium ion also indicates that the equilibrium (6) lies far towards the right.

The following equilibria may also exist in the solution.

Table 5. Dependence of rates for formic acid by BTMACB on substrate concentration in solvents of different compositions

 [BTMACB] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 298 K

Formic acid mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ k _{obs} /s ⁻¹ [at % AcOH (v/v)] ,				
	25	40	50	60	72
0.1	19.9	8.91	4.11	2.20	0.84
0.2	30.5	13.2	6.22	3.27	1.24
0.4	41.4	17.3	8.37	4.34	1.61
0.6	47.1	19.2	9.46	4.86	1.78
0.8	50.5	20.5	10.1	5.18	1.89
1.5	56.3	22.4	11.2	5.69	2.06
3.0	60.2	23.7	12.0	6.04	2.18
K (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)	4.45	5.51	4.72	5.20	5.82
10 ⁴ k ₂ (s ⁻¹)	64.7	25.1	12.8	6.42	2.30

The probable oxidizing species in a solution of BTMACB are, therefore, chlorobromate ion, molecular bromine or hypobromous acid. The equilibria (7) and (8) are likely to be suppressed by the addition of BTMACl or potassium bromide. The absence of any added BTMACl and bromide ion on the reaction rate rules out role of Br₂ and HOBr in the oxidation process. The oxidation of benzyl alcohol by bromine, in 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water, is retarded by the addition of bromide ions¹³ whereas the oxidation by BTMACB is unaffected by bromide ions. This indicates that in the present reaction bromine is not the active oxidizing species. Similar results were obtained in the oxidation of aliphatic aldehydes by BTMACB⁹. Thus in the present reaction also the reactive oxidizing species is the chlorobromate ion.

Solvent composition effect : The increase in the rate constant of disproportionation of the intermediate complex with an increase in the polarity of the medium suggests that the transition state is more polar than the reactants. The plot of log k₂ against the inverse of the dielectric constant is non-linear. The solvent effect was analysed using Grunwald-Winstein equation¹⁴.

$$\log k_2 = \log k_0 + mY \quad (9)$$

The plot of log k₂ versus Y is linear (r² = 0.9996) with m = 0.78 ± 0.01. The value of m suggests that there is a considerable charge separation in the transition state of the reaction.

Mechanism :

The presence of a substantial kinetic isotopic effect, in the oxidation of formic acid, confirmed that the α-C-H bond is cleaved in the rate-determining step. From the rate law, it

is apparent that an intermediate complex is formed in a rapid pre-equilibrium. The observed Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics with respect to the organic acid lead us to suggest that an intermediate complex may be formed by the interaction between the non-bonded pairs of electrons of carboxylic oxygen and BTMACB in a rapid pre-equilibrium (Scheme 1). The formation of similar complexes has also been postulated in the oxidation of aldehydes¹⁵ and diols¹⁶ with hexamethylenetetramine bromine (HABR) as well as in the oxidation of alcohols¹⁷ and organic acids¹⁸ by pyridinium hydrobromide perbromide (PHPB). The entropy of the complex formation in the oxidation of oxalic acid, is much more negative (*ca.* 3 times) than in the oxidation of formic acid. Thus BTMACB-OA complex, is more rigid than the BTMACB-FA complex. Hence, it is likely that, in the case of oxalic acid, both the carboxylic acid groups are involved

Scheme 1

in the complex formation. The experimental results can be accounted for the proposed mechanism in the terms of formation of cyclic/acyclic intermediate complexes in the pre-equilibrium and their subsequent decomposition in the rate-determining step.

The above mechanism is supported by the observed negative entropy of activation also. As the charge separation takes place, in the rate-determining step, the charged ends become highly solvated. This results in an immobilization of a large number of solvent molecules, reflected in the loss of entropy¹⁹. The low magnitude of ΔH^* and the large magnitude of ΔS^* indicate that the reaction is entropy controlled. The low value of ΔH^* also points out that in the rate-determining activated complex the bond-breaking and bond-formation are of almost equal magnitude.

Experimental

Materials : BTMACB and α -deuterioformic acid (DCOOH or DFA) were prepared by the reported methods^{1,20}. Formic and oxalic acids were commercial products of highest purity available and were used as supplied. The solutions of oxalic acid were prepared by direct weighing and those of formic acid were standardized by alkalimetry. Acetic acid was refluxed with chromic oxide and acetic anhydride and then fractionally distilled²¹.

Stoichiometry : To determine the stoichiometry, an excess of BTMACB ($\times 5$ or greater) was reacted with the organic acid in aqueous acetic acid solutions and allowed to stand for completion. The amount of residual BTMACB after the completion of reaction was measured spectrophotometrically at 394 nm. The results indicated 1 : 1 stoichiometry. No quantitative determination of carbon dioxide formed was carried out.

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the organic acid over BTMACB. The temperature was kept constant to ± 0.1 K. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v), unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of BTMACB spectrophotometrically at 394 nm for up to 80% of the reaction. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first-order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.995-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{BTMACB}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$.

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